

Digital Intellectual History of Modern Korean Literary Studies

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Data and Code <https://github.com/ByungjunKim/KoreanLitBibliometrics>

Research Questions

Discursive landscape of Korean literary studies and its dynamics in glocal context

3 Areas

- Korean literary studies in South Korea
- Global Korean literary studies
- English literary studies in South Korea

What are the main **characteristics** of each field, their **differences**, and **interrelationships**?

KCI Humanities Papers Publication Trends

Annual Publication Volume (2002-2024)

4,907
2002 Baseline

18,132
Peak (2014)

17,233
2024 Current

+251%
Total Growth

Rapid Growth Phase (2002-2015): 3.7x increase • Stabilization Period (2015-2024): ~17K papers annually

Data Sets

Korean literary studies in South Korea

- journal articles' metadata: Korea Citation Index 2008-2024
 - Abstracts available after 2008
- 52 academic journals in the field of Korean literature
- 17,510 articles

Data Sets

Global Korean literary studies

- journal articles' metadata: OpenAlex 2008-2024
- Keywords: Korean literature, culture, wave
- Korean literature: 220 articles
- Korean literature + culture + wave: 1,548 articles

Data Sets

English literary studies in South Korea

- journal articles' metadata
- *The Journal of English Language and Literature:*
1955-2024
 - Research Information Sharing Service 1955-2001
 - KCI 2002-2024
 - 2,580 articles
- 31 academic journals: KCI 2002-2024
 - 22,551 articles

Methodology

1. Semantic network analysis of keywords' co-occurrence in article titles
2. Structural Topic Modeling (STM)
 - Applied to Korean and English literary studies in South Korea
 - Not implemented for OpenAlex dataset due to limited data size
 - **Key advantage over traditional LDA:** STM enables statistical testing of **correlations between document metadata** (author's gender, publication year, etc.) and topic distributions.

Korean Literary Studies 2008-2024

Network Analysis

Feminism

Colonial Period Studies

KCI Korean literature 2008-2024, degree >= 1,500

Historical study of the (post)-colonial period

- ‘colony’, ‘Joseon’ (= Korea), ‘Japanese empire’, ‘Japan’, ‘nation’, ‘movement’, ‘liberation’, ‘war’, ‘North Korea’
- mainstream Korean literary study
- Post-colonialism?
- Rather “**colonial period studies**”
 - Study of modern Korean literature based on Korea’s own colonial experience

Feminism

- ‘woman’, ‘subject’, ‘representation’
- ‘memory’, ‘gender’, ‘ethics’, ‘desire’, ‘love’
 - ‘identity’, ‘sexuality’, ‘community’, ‘Other’, ‘gaze’, ‘family’, ‘violence’
- strong influence of **Western literary theory**
- When? What is behind this? Internal dynamics?

Korean Literary Studies 2008-2024

Structural Topic Modeling

R formula

- $\text{Topic} \sim \text{gender} * \text{publication year}$

11 topics (Based on semantic coherence and exclusivity)

Topic 7

'colonial', 'colony', 'nation', 'Joseon', 'empire' → **Colonial Period Studies**

Topic 7: 식민, 식민지, 민족, 조선, 제국

Topic 7:
식민, 식민지, 민족, 조선, 제국

Topic 9

'woman', 'man', 'gender', 'Other', 'body', 'worker', 'work', 'family' → **Feminism**

Topic 9: 여성, 남성, 젠더, 타자, 몸

Topic 9:
여성, 남성, 젠더, 타자, 몸

Red: female scholars

Feminism: dramatically increases after 2015

Why 2015? Emergence of female scholars

연도-성별 논문 생산 비중(현대문학 전체)

Global Korean Literary/Cultural Studies:
OpenAlex 2008-2024
Network Analysis

East Asian studies + comparative literature

- ‘chinese’, ‘japanese’, ‘north’, ‘south’, ‘korea’, ‘china’, ‘japan’, ‘joseon’
- ‘translation’, ‘comparative’, ‘comparison’

Diaspora

- Korean American literature: ‘american’, ‘hawaii’
- Koreans in Japan: ‘japan’, ‘zainichi’
- ‘ethnic’, ‘land’, ‘anti’, ‘sentiment’

‘empire’: most symptomatic node

- Colonialism issue is peripheral

OA Korean literature/Culture 2008-2024, degree ≥ 200

Korean pop culture industry dominates

- ‘wave’, ‘culture’, ‘cultural’, ‘hallyu’ (Korean Wave), ‘pop’, ‘popular’
- ‘drama’, ‘image’, ‘content’, ‘food’
- Commercial
 - ‘product’, ‘consumer’, ‘purchase’, ‘tourism’, ‘brand’, ‘industry’, ‘consumption’, ‘strategy’

English Literary Studies: *The Journal of
English Language and Literature* 1955-2024

Network Analysis

JELL 1955-2024, degree ≥ 50

Split or Duality

- Main characteristic of Korean English literary studies
- “Korean scholars studying English literature”
 - Korean vs. English
 - local vs. global
 - domestic vs. foreign
 - close vs. distant

1994

Top 15 Normalized Module Distribution per Year (1955-2024)

Something happened in 1994.

- Choice of academic language
 - Korean and English → Korean or English
- Dramatic increase of English literary studies written in Korean since 1994
- Increased self-consciousness
 - What it means to study English literature in South Korea
 - Drive to critically engage with English literature from a Korean perspective

Two completely different generations of scholarship

- post-Korean War generation: modernization → Westernization → Americanization
- 1987 generation: pro-democracy movement, politically charged

Paradigm shift

- Self-conscious, critical reception of English literature
- Socially critical and political
- Feminism, post-colonialism, and cultural studies

JELL 1994-2024, degree ≥ 50 , Korean

Korean: 'woman'

- key hub encompassing feminism and post-colonialism
- **Feminism:** 'subject', 'body', 'Other', 'gender', 'sexuality', 'feminism', 'feminist', 'desire'
- **Post-colonialism:** 'black', 'race', 'nation', 'imperialism', 'state', 'Indian', 'Coetzee', 'colonial', 'white', 'colonialism', 'post', 'nationalism'
- Political approach: 'politics', 'history', 'critique', 'political science', 'ideology', 'subversion', 'strategy'

JELL 1994-2024, degree ≥ 50 , English

English: slightly different, but similar

- 'world' 'literature'
- Post-colonialism: more prevalent than feminism
 - 'empire', 'race', 'black', 'postcolonial', 'asian', 'colonial', 'conrad', 'darkness', 'heart', 'imperial', 'difference', 'racial', 'nation', 'diasporic', 'transnational'
- Feminism
 - 'woman', 'sexual', 'mother', 'identity', 'mary', 'shelley', 'wollstonecraft', 'bronte'

Role of Korean English literary studies?

- Duality →
- **Mediator** between Korean literary studies and global literary discourses

English Literary Studies:
31 Academic Journals: 2002-2024
Network Analysis

KCI English literature (including linguistics) 2002-2024, degree \geq 500

‘woman’: key hub of English literary studies

- ‘subject’, ‘desire’, ‘representation’, ‘body’, ‘gender’, ‘Other’, ‘identity’
- ‘body’, ‘black’, ‘memory’, ‘race’, ‘violence’, ‘male’
- **Feminism + Post-colonialism**
- ‘narrative’, ‘representation’, ‘story’, ‘discourse’, ‘myth’
→ alternative discourse

‘America’

- connected to ‘woman’, ‘black’, ‘identity’, ‘culture’
- feminism, post-colonialism, cultural studies

‘woman’

- ‘female’, ‘body’, ‘desire’, ‘girl’, ‘lady’
- ‘morrison’, ‘black’, ‘white’, ‘man’, ‘race’, ‘racial’, ‘colonial’
- ‘memory’, ‘trauma’, ‘history’, ‘politics’, ‘anti’
- **Feminism + Post-colonialism**

‘american’

- ‘gender’, ‘asian’, ‘identity’, ‘representation’
- **Feminism + Post-colonialism**

‘yeats’

- ‘poetry’, ‘poetic’, ‘poetics’, ‘aesthetic’, ‘art’ → formal and aesthetic
- ‘politics’, ‘racial’, ‘female’, ‘body’, ‘colonial’, ‘political’
- **Feminism + Post-colonialism**

Political

- ‘power’, ‘subjectivity’, ‘political’, ‘cultural’, ‘culture’, ‘social’, ‘history’, ‘politics’, ‘critique’

English Literary Studies: 31 Academic Journals: 2002-2024

Structural Topic Modeling

R formula

- Topic ~ publication year

11 topics (gender data in progress, not included)

Topic 10

joyce, gender, feminism, masculinity, space, sexuality, nationalism, ulysses, imperialism → **Feminism + Post-colonialism**

Topic 10: joyce, gender, feminism, masculinity, space

Topic 9

memory, trauma, toni_morrison, war, community, history, family, racism, slave, violence → **Post-colonialism**

Topic 9: memory, trauma, toni_morrison, war, community

Decreasing Topics

Topic 3 (17th and 18th Century English Literature), Topic 5 (19th Century American Literature), Topic 8 (Narratology) → **Canonical, formalist studies**

Topic 3: john, milton, century, capitalism, england

Topic 5: love, hawthorne, god, myth, romance

Topic 8: story, time, character, reality, film

Conclusion

Korean literary studies in South Korea

- Colonial Period Studies
 - mainstream Korean literary study
 - male scholars
 - declining dramatically
- Feminism and Cultural Studies
 - increasing drastically since 2015
 - female scholars
 - strong influence of global literary theories

Conclusion

Global Korean literary/cultural studies

- Korean pop culture industry dominates
 - commercial
- Literature: East Asian comparative studies
 - Diaspora
 - Colonialism is peripheral
- Quite different from Korean literary studies in South Korea

Conclusion

English literary studies in South Korea

- New generation of English literary scholars since 1994
- Feminism, Post-colonialism, Cultural Studies
- **Mediator** between Korean literary studies and global literary discourses
 - Western feminist theories and literary studies + Korean literary academia
 - Korean colonial period studies + global post-colonial theory
- Played a key role in connecting Korean literary studies to global literary discourses

Future Studies

1. Enhanced Demographic Modeling

- Incorporate comprehensive researcher demographic data for more sophisticated analysis
- Korean literary studies: 80% gender matching completed
- English literary studies: Researcher demographic matching in progress

2. Citation Network Analysis

- Leverage bibliographic reference data to map scholarly influence patterns
- Previous research reveals gender and generational preferences in citation practices
- Specific authors and even particular works show different citation patterns (e.g., Foucault's "Heterotopias")
- Reference data will enable more nuanced tracking of academic field dynamics and theoretical migrations

Appendix

Methodology: Text Preprocessing for STM

1. Text Data Preparation

- Combined article titles, keywords, and abstracts as training corpus
- Extracted only nouns (including proper nouns) for analysis

2. Morphological Analysis

- **Korean:** [Kiwi](#) 0.21 morphological analyzer
- **English:** spaCy 3.8.7 with en_core_web_trf model

3. N-gram Processing (using ‘_’)

- **Bigram:** Words appearing 100+ times and frequently co-occurring were merged with underscores
- **Trigram:** For English literature data, additional trigram processing applied to terms appearing 50+ times after bigram processing

Methodology: STM Document Preparation

Document Filtering Process

Korean Literary Studies

- Applied lower threshold of 400 documents
- Words must appear in 400+ documents to be included
- **Result:** 565 words used for STM training

English Literary Studies

- Applied lower threshold of 100 documents
- Words must appear in 100+ documents to be included
- **Result:** 517 words used for STM training

Purpose: Remove rare words to improve model stability and focus on significant vocabulary patterns

Methodology: Optimal Topic Number Selection in Kor. Lit.

Diagnostic Values by Number of Topics

Semantic Coherence vs Exclusivity by Number of Topics (K)

4

Methodology: Optimal Topic Number Selection in Eng. Lit.

Diagnostic Values by Number of Topics

Semantic Coherence vs Exclusivity by Number of Topics (K)

Korean Literary Studies - Topic Keywords (FREX)

Topic	Theme	Korean Keywords (FREX Top 10)	English Keywords (FREX Top 10)
Topic 1	Narratology	소설, 서사, 인물, 이야기, 서술, 작가, 장편, 사건, 주인공, 단편	Novel, Narrative, Character, Story, Narration, Writer, Full-length, Event, Protagonist, Short story
Topic 2	Modern Korean Literature	번역, 근대, 이광수, 신문, 계몽, 독자, 중국, 출판, 전통, 언어	Translation, Modern, Lee Gwangsu, Newspaper, Enlightenment, Reader, China, Publication, Tradition, Language
Topic 3	North Korean Literature	북한, 아동, 창작, 발표, 문예, 작품, 활동, 동화, 사회주의, 잡지	North Korea, Children, Creation, Publication, Literature, Work, Activity, Fairy tale, Socialism, Magazine
Topic 4	Post-war Popular Culture	영화, 전쟁, 문화, 대중, 미국, 한국, 냉전, 반공, 전후, 세대	Film, War, Culture, Mass, America, Korea, Cold War, Anti-communist, Post-war, Generation
Topic 5	Modern Space	공간, 장소, 도시, 기억, 고향, 시간, 과거, 서울, 체험, 신화	Space, Place, City, Memory, Hometown, Time, Past, Seoul, Experience, Myth
Topic 6	Ethics (Western Theory)	인간, 사랑, 죽음, 폭력, 자유, 윤리, 감정, 개인, 법, 공동체	Human, Love, Death, Violence, Freedom, Ethics, Emotion, Individual, Law, Community
Topic 7	Colonial Period Studies	식민, 식민지, 민족, 조선, 제국, 국민, 국가, 조선인, 일본, 해방	Colonial, Colony, Nation, Joseon, Empire, People, State, Korean, Japan, Liberation
Topic 8	Literary History	문학, 지역, 문학사, 비평, 예술, 민중, 운동, 문인, 문단, 현대	Literature, Region, Literary History, Criticism, Art, People, Movement, Writer, Literary circle, Modern
Topic 9	Feminism	여성, 남성, 젠더, 타자, 몸, 노동자, 노동, 가족, 주체, 가부장	Woman, Male, Gender, Other, Body, Worker, Labor, Family, Subject, Patriarchy
Topic 10	Education	교육, 글쓰기, 과학, 기술, 대학, 이론, 교양, 지식, 방법, 활용	Education, Writing, Science, Technology, University, Theory, Liberal arts, Knowledge, Method, Application
Topic 11	Poetics	시, 시인, 이미지, 자연, 시집, 자아, 이상, 감각, 미학, 서정	Poetry, Poet, Image, Nature, Poetry collection, Self, Ideal, Sense, Aesthetics, Lyricism

English Literary Studies in South Korea - Topic Keywords (FREX)

Topic	Theme	Keywords (FREX Top 10)
Topic 1	Translation	translation, modernity, culture, writing, studies, text, machine, style, literary, policy
Topic 2	EFL (English as a Foreign Language)	reading, l2, speaker, strategy, knowledge, anxiety, vocabulary, acquisition, use, effect
Topic 3	17th and 18th Century English Literature	john, milton, century, capitalism, england, satire, james, society, robert, elizabeth
Topic 4	Linguistics	verb, construction, movement, metaphor, feature, constraint, clause, object, structure, theory
Topic 5	19th Century American Literature	love, hawthorne, god, myth, romance, marriage, irony, death, self, song
Topic 6	Poetics	yeats, poetry, eliot, poem, t_s_eliot, wordsworth, w_b_yeats, poet, lawrence, poetics
Topic 7	Shakespeare	shakespeare, hamlet, drama, law, body, tragedy, ethic, ethics, play, theatre
Topic 8	Narratology	story, time, character, reality, film, narrator, world, hero, sense, work
Topic 9	Post-Colonialism	memory, trauma, toni_morrison, war, community, history, family, racism, slave, violence
Topic 10	Feminism & Post-Colonialism	joyce, gender, feminism, masculinity, space, sexuality, nationalism, james_joyce, ulysses, imperialism
Topic 11	English Education	teacher, education, teaching, school, learning, student, textbook, program, curriculum, perception